

An Evolutionary Deep Learning Approach for Efficient Quantum Algorithms Transpilation

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Abstract. Gate-based quantum computation describes algorithms as quantum circuits. These can be seen as a set of quantum gates acting on a set of qubits. To be executable, the circuit requires complex transformations to comply with the physical constraints of the machines. This process is known as transpilation, where qubits' layout initialisation is one of its first and most challenging steps, usually done by considering the device error properties. As the size of the quantum algorithm increases, the transpilation becomes increasingly complex and time-consuming. This constitutes a bottleneck towards agile, fast, and error-robust quantum computation. This work proposes an evolutionary deep neural network that learns the qubits' layout initialisation of the most advanced and complex IBM heuristic used in today's quantum machines. The aim is to progressively replace weakly scalable transpilation heuristics with machine learning models. Previous work using machine learning models for qubits' layout initialisation suffers from some shortcomings in the proposal's correctness and generalisation as well as benchmarks diversity, utility, and availability. The present work solves those flaws by (I) devising a complete Machine Learning pipeline including the ETL component and the evolutionary deep neural model using the linkage learning algorithm P3, (II) a modelling applicable to any quantum algorithm with a special interest to both optimisation and machine learning ones, (III) diverse and fresh benchmarks using calibration data of four real IBM quantum computers collected over 10 months (Dec. 2022 and Oct. 2023) and training dataset built using four types of quantum optimisation and machine learning algorithms, as well as random ones. The proposal has been proven to be more efficient and simple than state-of-the-art deep neural models in the literature.

Keywords: Evolutionary Machine Learning · Deep Neural Architecture Search · Quantum Variational Algorithms · Quantum Transpilation.

1 Introduction

Gate-based quantum computers express computation as quantum circuits, seen as a series of quantum gates acting on a set of quantum bits (or qubits). Current devices are in their Noisy Intermediate Scale Era (NISQ), having a noisy

nature and a limited number of qubits (10 to 100s), not enough to implement efficient quantum error correction [3]. To be executable on quantum machines, such types of quantum algorithms undergo a series of complex transformations, usually known as transpilation, to comply with the hardware constraints of the quantum machine. The transpilation process has a major influence on the efficiency and reliability of quantum computation, especially considering the NISQ nature of today’s quantum computers. Qubits’ layout initialisation is one of the first, most critical and challenging steps in the transpilation proven to be NP-complete [16]. Due to the complexity of such a task, a good amount of research work can be found in the literature focused on the qubits’ initialisation³, covering several quantum technologies with different approaches. This work focuses on superconducting quantum computers, in particular, IBM quantum computers, considering that they are one of the most investigated and actively deployed in the industry. Most literature (around 68 works in total) and today’s transpilers rely on exact [16] or heuristic-based approaches [17]. For small-sized circuits, the transpilation remains decently fast. However, the time increases drastically when the complexity of the algorithms increases (e.g. the authors found that transpiling GHZ circuits on 5627-qubits machines takes around 8.89 hours). Clearly, time is a key factor in quantum computation considering that today’s quantum hardware is timely limited and affected by noise. Also, tedious and long transpilation might make quantum advantage vanish when an equivalent classical algorithms runs in the same time.

As an alternative to exact and heuristic-based transpilation approaches for qubit initialisation, efforts are made to devise machine-learning-based qubits’ initialisers instead. Indeed, heuristics need to run the same costly computation each time a quantum circuit (algorithm) is given (whether used or not before), while Machine Learning (ML) ones would be trained only once profiting from past data. To the best of the authors’ knowledge, only three works have explored such an alternative [1, 10, 11]. Although promising, these former works have shortfalls on several levels, such as incorrect modelling of the qubits’ initialisation as a machine learning task which threatens the proposal’s reliability. Also, they focus only on the deep learning model, although the entire Extract-Transform-Load (ETL) is quite critical whether for the experiments’ reproducibility or their use in on-production transpilers. Moreover, the used benchmarks are not always accessible, they are outdated and limited in terms of complexity, diversity, and utility of the used quantum algorithms and machines. This does not properly reflect the advances in quantum hardware (e.g., noise resilience, error probabilities, etc.) neither the generalisation of the approach to useful quantum algorithms. The present work copes with those shortfalls by (I) devising a correct and generalisable ML task modelling of the qubits’ initialisation problem; (II) devising an entire pipeline including both the ETL components and a deep learning model that is evolved using a linkage learning algorithm known as the Parameter-less Population Pyramid (P3) [7]; and (III) using a diverse benchmark built using continuously-up-to-date noise-calibration data of four real IBM quantum ma-

³ For the sake of brevity, we omit the word “layout” in “qubits’ layout initialization”.

chines over 10 months (Dec. 2022 to Oct. 2023) and a wide range of quantum algorithms including QAOA, quantum classifier, QGANs, and random circuits.

In the rest of the paper we introduce the fundamentals of quantum computation and transpilation in Section 2, and we present the neural architecture search in Section 3. Section 4 presents the proposed approach, while Section 5 experimentally investigates the proposal. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2 Preliminary Concepts

Two quantum computation paradigms exist: adiabatic and gate-based. The first is based on the adiabatic theorem and is dedicated to solving optimisation problems, while the second is a more universal one and has a large range of applications attracting both the interest of Industry and Academia.

We focus in this paper on the gate-based paradigm, which describes computations as quantum circuits (see Fig. 1(a)) composed of a series of *quantum gates* acting on quantum bits (qubits). A qubit state $|\psi\rangle$ is, in general, a superposition of two base states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$, where $|\psi\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C}$. They also verify the normalisation condition $|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 = 1$. The quantum state of a multiple-qubits system can be represented by the tensor product of the qubits' quantum state $|\psi\rangle = \bigotimes_{i=1}^n |\psi_i\rangle$, where $|\psi_i\rangle \in \mathbb{C}^{2^n}$. Mathematically, each quantum gate is represented by a *unitary transformation* $U : \mathbb{C}^{2^n} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}^{2^n}$, which verifies $U^\dagger U = U U^\dagger = I$, where U^\dagger is the Hermitian adjoint of U and I is the identity matrix. Several quantum gates exist [13] such as the Hadamard H gate, Pauli gates $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$, etc.

Fig. 1. (a) Quantum circuit, (b) QPU topology and (c) qubits' initialisation

To be executable on gate-based quantum computers, quantum algorithms undergo a *transpilation* process. Transpilation consists in a series of complex and chained tasks to translate the original quantum circuit into another one that fulfills the machines' constraints (e.g., available gates) [17]. Each manufacturer has its own transpilation process with different phases. Indeed, from one work to another (e.g. compilation, synthesis, etc.), and eventually from one manufacturer to another (e.g. IBM: passes, Google: Transformers, etc.), the transpilation process can be named or executed differently. The quality of the transpilation process has a huge impact on the error-robustness, correctness and feasibility of the computation, especially considering the NISQ era of quantum devices. The

circuit’s depth is a reliable metric of such quality, where for a gate g with a predecessor $P(g)$, the $\text{depth}(g)$ is defined by Equation (1). The depth of the circuit is the maximum value of $\text{depth}(g)$ over all gates g . In that sense, a special interest is given here to the IBM transpilation process, since it is the most representative and white-boxed one. More particularly, the focus of this work is on the qubits’ initialisation problem within IBM quantum machines [5].

$$\text{depth}(g) \triangleq \begin{cases} 0 & P(g) = \emptyset \\ 1 + \max_{p \in P(g)} \text{depth}(p) & P(g) \neq \emptyset \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The qubits’ initialisation problem is one of the first and most critical transpilation steps. It is proven to be NP-complete [16] and omnipresent in most of today’s quantum machines (e.g., IBM, Google, etc.), and spans over several technologies such as superconducting and Ion-trapped qubits [2, 21]. Having a quantum circuit C acting on a set of N logical qubits $Q = \{q_1, \dots, q_N\}$, the qubits’ initialisation problem consists in mapping the set of logical qubits Q to a set of M physical qubits $P = \{p_1, \dots, p_M\}$ on the Quantum Processing Unit (QPU), where $M \geq N$ (see Fig. 1(c)). A solution X to this problem would be one of the possible ${}_M P_N$ permutations without repetition (partial or complete depending on whether $M = N$ or not) formed by the arrangement of N physical qubits from $\{p_1, \dots, p_M\}$. In this work, it is admitted that no matter what the arrangement is, the logical qubits (q_1, \dots, q_N) would be assigned to physical qubits according to a natural order. Meaning, a permutation $(p_1, p_5, p_2, p_4, p_3)$ would represent a solution where q_1 is assigned to p_1 , q_2 to p_5 , q_3 to p_2 , q_4 to p_4 , and q_5 to p_3 . The quality of a solution has a direct effect on the remaining phases of the transpilation (e.g. qubit routing, optimisation via transitivity and cancellation rules, etc.), the feasibility of computation and its noise-robustness.

3 Deep Learning and Neural Architecture Search

The goal of *supervised learning* is to build a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$ fitting a set of samples $(x, y) \in X \times Y$. There are many techniques for supervised learning. We focus here on *deep learning* models and, in particular, *deep neural networks* (DNNs). A deep neural network is composed of several layers of neurons (Figure 2(b)). Neurons in the *input layer* represent the input vector x , while the neurons in layer j receive as input the output of layer $j - 1$. This input is weighted and summed before computing an activation function a . The output of the neuron is given by the expression $a(\sum_{i=1}^{n_{(j-1)}} w_i^{(j)} x_i^{(j-1)} + b)$, where $x_i^{(j-1)}$ is the output of the i -th neuron in layer $j - 1$ and $n_{(j-1)}$ is the number of neurons at layer $j - 1$ (see Figure 2(a)). The goal of the learning process is to find an optimal or sufficiently close to optimal set of connection weights $w_i^{(j)}$. Several factors influence the efficiency of neural networks. For instance, the architecture, the training algorithm, and the choice of features used in training. Training is performed using gradient-descent techniques to minimise a loss function [18].

Fig. 2. (a) DNN principle and (b) neural architecture search

Evolutionary computation has been used to enhance the efficiency of machine learning (ML) techniques principally in pre-processing (e.g., feature selection and re-sampling), learning (e.g., parameter setting, membership functions, and neural network topology), and post-processing (e.g., rule optimisation, decision tree/support vectors pruning, etc.). Several well-known EAs exist, although the interest in this paper focuses on *linkage learning* EAs. They represent solutions as d -dimensional vectors and try to learn the relations among the d decision variables to be more efficient during the search. This class of algorithms have been profoundly studied and led to promising advances. One can cite as examples, the LTGA (Linkage Tree Genetic Algorithm) [19], LT-GOMEA (Linkage Tree Gene-pool Optimal Mixing Evolutionary Algorithm) [20], the DSMGA-II (Dependency Structure Matrix Genetic Algorithm II) [9], the 3LOa (Linkage Learning based on Local Optimisation algorithm) [15] and the P3 [7], which we use in this work. We use in this work linkage learning algorithms in Neural Architecture Search (NAS) where the DNN topology is evolved using P3, while the learning process is left to gradient descent approaches [18] (see Fig. 2(b)). Although applying EAs for NAS has been quite investigated, to the best of the authors' knowledge, linkage learning algorithms have never been applied to NAS.

3.1 Deep Learning For Qubits' Initialisation

To the best of the authors' knowledge, there are 68 works that tackle the qubits' initialisation problem whether as a standalone problem [5] or jointly with other transpilation problems [17]. Most of those works approach the problem using exact algorithms with high computational cost as the problem's size increases, or heuristic ones that are meant to be less computational greedy. Unlike previous literature, works in [1, 10, 11] started exploring the use of deep learning to solve the qubits' initialisation problem. Although, it is worth noting that the works in [10, 11] present the same proposal. The authors in [1] propose a DNN model to tackle the qubits' initialisation as a classification problem. The aim is to learn the initialisation produced by a noise-aware heuristic used in today's IBM quantum machines [12]. That work suffers from some shortfalls. First, the modelling of the qubits' initialisation as a machine learning problem is not completely reliable or generalisable. Actually, it only considers very limited calibration parameters such

as T_1 , T_2 , **CNOT error** and **execution time** as well as **readout error**, while when having a quantum machine with k qubits and n qubits' connectivities, $8k + 2 \cdot 5 + 2n$ important calibration parameters exist. Also, the circuits modelling does not capture the sequencing of gates execution. Indeed, using the devised modelling, several circuits might be modeled using the same representation, while requiring different intialisation. This turns out to be quite challenging in ML. The benchmark they use is composed of purely random circuits with no known utility and uses only one 5-qubit machine topology called **IBM Q Burlington** whose calibration data dates back to 2021. This prevents assessing the proposal on quantum algorithms of known use (e.g., optimisation, machine learning, etc.). Another problem is that the machine used has been retired by IBM, so the practical interest of the paper is limited.

The authors in [10, 11] combine reinforcement learning with a graph neural network to solve the qubits' initialisation problem. Likewise in [1], the authors used an ML task modelling that is not completely reliable or generalisable. Indeed, calibration data such as the **reset gates length** are discarded, as well as an important parameter such as the **readout length**. The circuits modelling is restricted to only four gates, which are not universal. This restricts the generalisation of the approach to other quantum circuits. Most importantly, the circuits feature modelling does not capture the sequencing of the gates which is crucial. Moreover, the authors use only two quantum machines of 7 and 27 qubits (**IBM Nairobi** and **Algiers**) and study only 6 quantum circuits. The dataset they use is not made available, which prevents any replication of the results. Last, but not least, all the work done in [1, 10, 11] focuses only on devising the DNN model and discards other important components in any ML pipeline, especially the ETL part. This prevents the proposal from being constantly up-to-date with the quantum hardware evolution (e.g., noise sensitivity) and therefore any integration in on-production quantum transpilers.

This work attempts to correct all the shortfalls identified in [1, 10, 11], but it still goes in the same sense as the work done in [1] by learning the qubits' initialisation produced by the IBM heuristic called **Noise Adaptive** [12].

4 The Proposed Approach

The proposal aims at coping with the shortfalls identified in the previous work: (I) the machine learning task modelling, (II) the proposal's completeness and efficiency, as well as (III) the benchmark diversity/utility and availability. Figure 3 sketches the two main modules of our proposal and their execution flow. The next subsections explain these modules in detail. Also, the full source code of the proposal is made publicly available in [4].

4.1 The Extract-Transform-Load Module

We will start describing the ETL module and its components in this section.

Fig. 3. The modules and components of the proposed approach

The Extraction Component: This component is a scraper responsible for the extraction of daily fresh calibration data of all the available IBM quantum machines. It automatically detects which machine(s) is(are) available as well as the quantum transpiler version locally installed. Therefore, it changes automatically the scrapping mechanism as well as handling the servers' failures according to transpiler's versioning. The extraction is performed every 30 minutes. The calibration data being extracted represent the physical properties (e.g., error, execution time, etc.) of both the qubits and the implementable quantum gates on it. As to the qubits, there are 8 calibration parameters extracted for each qubit: the **decoherence times** (in μs) T_1 and T_2 , the frequency and anharmonicity (in GHz), the **readout error probability** and **length** (in ns), the **error probability** of measuring the state $|1\rangle$ when preparing it in $|0\rangle$ and vice versa. As to the quantum gates, two pieces of data are extracted; the **gate error probability** and the **gate length** (in ns) for all possible single (I , R_Z , S^\dagger , σ_x , **reset**) and all two-qubits gates (i.e., CNOT). In total, having a quantum machine with k qubits and n qubits' connectivities, $8k$ qubit parameters and $2 \cdot 5 + 2n$ gate parameters will be extracted for each of the 4 IBM quantum machines found available: `ibmq_lima`, `ibmq_belem`, `ibmq_quito` and `ibmq_manila`. So, far, data of 11 months have been gathered from the 12th December 2022 to the 2nd October 2023. The scraper is continuously being executed (24H a day and 7 days a week) to gather new data. The raw calibration data are made available for open public use at [4]. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first time in the literature that such scraper has been devised and made available together with real world data of this amount and diversity.

The Transformation Component: To correct the modelling previously presented in [1], we propose a modelling based on three components (see Figure 4): (I) the quantum machine calibration, (II) the quantum machine topology and (III) the quantum circuit.

The first one corresponds to the calibration of the quantum machine. Unlike the previous works [1, 10, 11], which considers only some calibration data while neglecting others, the presented modelling includes the totality of the data extracted by the extraction component previously introduced. The IBM heuristic **Noise Adaptive** considers most of those calibration data to calculate the initial

Fig. 4. Representation of ML features generated by transformation component

qubits' placement (see Figure 4(a)). This approach allows our proposal to identify uniquely each machine, therefore avoiding that several samples represent multiple machines. The second part of the modelling is dedicated to representing the topology of the qubits' connectivity of the quantum machine. This turns out to be quite important in order to devise a proposal able to learn the **Noise Adaptive** qubits' intialisation for any quantum machine topology, instead of focusing on one concrete quantum machine (requiring a separate learning process for each machine). The features that represent the topology are a flattened vector of the adjacency matrix of the underlying graph representing the quantum device qubits' connectivity (see Figure 4(b)).

The third part of the modelling concerns the quantum algorithm itself. Indeed, previous work considers a set of features that does not represent circuits in a unique way: it might map several quantum algorithms to the same representation. In fact, those representation-equivalent algorithms could need a different qubits' initialisation. In the present modelling, the circuit is decomposed into layers, where each layer regroups the gates that can be executed in parallel (see Figure 4(c)). Therefore a circuit with d gates, would be translated into features by representing each gate in each layer sequentially using a sequence of three digits $\{x_i, y_i, z_i\}$, $i = 1, \dots, d$, where the first digit x_i identifies the type of gate and the two remaining digits y_i and z_i are dedicated to represent the ID of the qubits taking part in the gate execution. In single-qubit gates, the two digits y_i and z_i will represent the (same) ID of the qubit the gate affects (see Figure 4).

Unlike the previous literature, which studied either random circuits with no known utility [1], or a set of limited quantum algorithms like in [10, 11], in this work the training data is generated by considering four types of algorithms dedicated to optimisation, machine learning and random ones. This way we maximise the generalisation of the devised approach. In particular, we consider the Quantum Approximate Optimisation Algorithm (QAOA) [6], the Quantum Variational Classifier (QVC) and the Quantum Adversarial Neural Network (QGAN) [8]. The QAOA has been used by setting the depth to 1, while the QVC was used with a fully-entangled mapping and classification with depth 1. The QGAN has been built by considering a fully-entangled discriminator and generator with depth 1. Both the QVC and QGAN features' mapping parts have been generated using the R_z , R_y and CR_z quantum gates. The mathematical details of the

QAOA, QVC and QGAN go beyond the scope of this work. For further details, please refer to the original works [6, 8].

In QAOA, a random instance of the Quadratic Unconstrained Binary Optimisation Problem (QUBO) is solved each time, while the random quantum circuits are generated by considering a universal set of quantum gates: CNOT, H, S and T. The encoding handled by our approach has been thought to go beyond the previous set of gates and can cover a large plethora of quantum gates, such as H, S, T, R_Z , σ_x , U_1 , U and CNOT. In all the quantum circuits, a maximum depth of 200 gates is considered. For those quantum algorithms that do not consume all the gates' depth, a padding of zeros is added in their features' vector. So far, the generated dataset contains over 31,109 training samples. The code of the transformation component automatically generates a fresh training dataset (when needed) if new quantum machines/calibration data are available or there is a need for other datasets built using different quantum algorithms.

Moving now to the targets of the training dataset, they have been generated by executing the generated circuits (QAOA, QVC, QGAN or random) using the IBM transpiler by setting it to the third level of optimisation (most sophisticated and costly one) and imposing the **Noise Adaptive** heuristic for qubits' initialisation. The transpiler is executed over 30 executions and the qubits initialisation that produces the circuit with the smallest circuit depth (see Equation (1)) is the one considered as a target for the generated features. Having a quantum machine of n qubits, targets will be organised as tuples of shape $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, where the rank i of the value in the tuple represents the logical qubit that will be placed in the x_i^{th} physical qubit. For instance, the configuration $\{5, 4, 1\}$ indicates that the 1^{st} logical qubit will be placed on the 5^{th} physical one, the 2^{nd} on the 4^{th} , and the 3^{rd} on the 1^{st} .

The Loading Component: The loading component is responsible for the persistence of the training dataset as well as the raw data. This information is stored in “.csv” files considering that the proposal in its current form is meant for direct integration in the IBM transpiler or other CLI standalone use. Indeed, ML libraries such as Scikit-learn, Tensorflow, Pytorch, and Keras, have some readiness to use .csv files via **Pandas** more than other types of files. However, if any API-based use is planned for the proposal, the switch to “.json” files is thought to be quite straightforward and easy to accomplish.

4.2 The Evolutionary Deep Neural Network Module

This section presents the evolutionary deep learning module that will be trained on the data generated by the ETL module (see Section 4.1), and learns the qubits' initialisation generated by the IBM transpiling heuristic **Noise Adaptive**.

The Pre-processing Component: Before feeding the training samples generated by the ETL module to the deep neural network, the training dataset is

normalised and reduced. Concretely, as for normalisation the Z-score normalisation is applied to convert the dataset samples in such a way that the mean is 0 and the deviation is equal to 1 using the $\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}$, where μ is the mean of the data and σ is the standard deviation. As a feature reduction, the Principal Component Analysis technique is used with the goal of finding the linear transformation that keeps the variance at maximum using the minimum number of features [14].

The Deep Neural Network Component: The qubits’ initialisation is modeled as a multi-class classification problem. Given a quantum algorithm that acts on q qubits and a quantum machine with n qubits, the idea is to determine which of the $1, \dots, n$ physical qubits (classes) is used for each logical qubit. The original architecture used in this work is the one presented in [1]. The choice was made for this model because it is the one providing the best results so far on this problem (see Figure 5).

Fig. 5. The used state-of-the-art deep neural network

We can see the DNN model as the union of several sub-DNN models that are trained separately to decide the physical qubit in which a logical qubit is mapped. All neurons in the DNN model are densely connected. Every neural layer uses the ReLU activation function $a(x) = \max(0, x)$ except the dropout and

the output layer that uses a `softmax` function. The output generated by the ETL module is converted into an array of probabilities, where each n variables constitutes the probability of a given logical qubit to be assigned to each physical qubit of the machine.

The Evolutionary Neural Architecture Search Component: The original model presented in [1] is composed of several neural layers of sizes 264, 1024, 256, and 128 (see Figure 5). The idea in our proposal is to decide the model’s architecture as well as some other hyper-parameters using an evolutionary algorithm to reduce to loss function. As loss function, we use the average of the categorical cross-entropy of each sub-DNN model presented in the previous section. The variables to be optimised are the size of each neural layer of the DNN model as well as the number of training epochs and the batch size. In total, 6 optimisation variables $x_{j=1,\dots,6} \in \mathbb{N}$ are considered (the dropout layer is neglected). Each variable might evolve from the original value used in [1], and $\frac{1}{4}$ of that value, except for the batch size that is allowed to take values up to $\frac{1}{8}$ of the original value. Such a choice of lower bounds is thought to explore if the P3 can reduce the complexity of the model while enhancing (or at least maintaining) its efficiency.

The solution encoding considered in this proposal is binary, where each integer decision variable $y_{j=1,\dots,6} \in \mathbb{N}$ is encoded using m bits. Let x be the bitstring representing variable y , the expression for y is:

$$y = l + (1 - 2^{m-1} + u - l)x_{m-1} + \sum_{i=0}^{m-2} 2^i x_i, \quad (2)$$

which ensures that $l \leq y_{j=1,\dots,6} \leq u$. In the previous expression, l and u represents the minimum and maximum value a decision variable can take. In this work, l is $u/4$ or $u/8$, depending on the decision variable. Having k logical qubits required by the quantum algorithm, and n physical ones on the QPU, and d training samples, the objective function to minimize is defined by

$$f(W) = -\frac{1}{k} \sum_{l=1}^k \frac{1}{d} \sum_{i=1}^d \sum_{j=1}^n t_{(i,l,j)} \log(p_{(i,l,j)}), \quad (3)$$

where $t_{(i,l,j)}$ is 1 if sample i assigns logical qubit l to physical qubit j and 0 otherwise, and $p_{(i,l,j)}$ is the prediction returned by the `softmax` activation function for sample i on the physical qubit j assigned to logical qubit l .

We use the original version of the P3 algorithm to solve this problem. Algorithm 1 sketches the general framework of the P3, while further technical details can be found in the original work [7].

5 Experimental Study

This section presents the experimental design, results, and their discussion in the next three subsections.

Algorithm 1 The P3 pseudo-code

```

1: Create random solution
2: Apply hill climber
3: if solution  $\notin$  hashset then
4:   Add solution to  $P_0$ 
5:   Add solution to hashset
6: end if
7: while  $\exists P_i \in$  pyramid not processed do
8:   Mix solution with  $P_i$ 
9:   if solution’s fitness has improved then
10:    if solution  $\notin$  hashset then
11:      Add solution to  $P_{i+1}$ 
12:      Add solution to hashset
13:    end if
14:  end if
15: end while

```

5.1 Experiments’ Design and Benchmarks

The implementation has been done using both `python` version 3.10.2 and `C++` with a `GCC` version 11.4.0. We use a machine running Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS 64 bits (7 CPUs and 16 GB of RAM) and Linux Enterprise Server 15 SP4 15.4 OS. The ETL module has been built using IBM quantum kit (Qiskit) version 0.44.2, while the evolutionary deep-learning module has been built using the libraries `scikit-learn` version 1.3.2, `Tensorflow` version 2.14.0 and `Keras` version 2.14.0. The source code of P3 is the one made publicly available by the authors⁴, slightly modified to execute within our framework, including the cluster execution. All the code generated, the datasets and the results are published in a replication package in Zenodo [4]. All the experiments have been run in a cluster with the configuration given in Table 1.

Table 1. Hardware components of the cluster used.

Nodes	CPU / GPU	RAM	InfiniBand	Localscratch
126 \times SD530	56 \times Intel Xeon Gold 6230R @ 2.10GHz	200GB	HDR100	950 GB
24 \times Bu11 R282-Z90	128 \times AMD EPYC 7H12 @ 2.6GHz	2TB	HDR200	3.5TB
168 \times IBM dx360 M4	16 \times Intel E5-2670 @ 2.6GHz	32GB	FDR40	400GB
4 \times DGX-A100	8 \times A100 Tensor Core	1TB		14 TB

The comparison basis in this work is composed of the state-of-the-art DNN model devised in [1] (SOTA-DNN) and the newly proposed evolutionary DNN using the P3 algorithm (P3-DNN). The original DNN model has been executed using the same parameters as the ones given in [1]. This includes the same neural layers’ dimension (i.e., 264, 1024, 256, and 128), the same batch size of 128

⁴ <https://github.com/brianwgoldman/FastEfficientP3>

and 150 training epochs, and Adam as a learning algorithm with learning rate of 0.0005. Regarding P3, the only parameter it has is the stopping condition, which has been set to 1000 fitness evaluations. Each experiment, whether using the SOTA-DNN or P3-DNN, has been performed over 32 independent executions. Metrics such as the Best, Worst, Median and Median Absolute Deviation (MAD) of the results across all the executions have been recorded.

5.2 Results and Discussion

Table 2 presents the average categorical cross-entropy loss obtained by SOTA-DNN and P3-DNN over all the circuits. The best results are highlighted in bold on the basis of the Median metric. The proposed P3-DNN achieves better results than SOTA-DNN in all the considered metrics.

Table 2. Average categorical cross-entropy loss of SOTA-DNN and P3-DNN over all the quantum circuits.

Model	Best	Worst	Median	MAD
SOTA-DNN	3.1856	9.9488	5.2786	0.9618
P3-DNN	2.6378	5.4681	3.2379	0.3076

Interestingly, P3-DNN outperforms SOTA-DNN using a deep neural network that is simpler and easier to train than the original one. While SOTA-DNN is composed of 264, 1024, 256, and 128 neurons in each layer and uses a batch size equal to 128 samples trained over 150 epochs, P3-DNN is composed of 118, 736, 177 and 122 neurons only in each layer and uses batches of size 67 samples trained over 55 epochs. Concretely the SOTA-DNN has 1757929 parameters to train ($6864 + 271360 + (5 \cdot 262400) + (5 \cdot 32896) + (5 \cdot 645)$), while the P3-DNN has only 854552 parameters to train ($3068 + 87584 + (5 \cdot 130449) + (5 \cdot 21716) + (5 \cdot 615)$). This indicates that the proposed P3-DNN has reduced the complexity of the model to almost half of the original SOTA-DNN complexity (48.611%).

Figure 6 illustrates a zoom-in on the fitness value evolution of the P3 in one of the best executions, during the first fitness evaluations. It can be seen that the P3 has considerably reduced the loss during the first iterations without consuming yet the 1000 fitness evaluations budget. This might suggest that racing methods combined with P3 could be interesting to investigate to make the P3 even more efficient.

Although finding the adequate DNN architecture using the P3 might take longer than executing directly the original DNN architecture given in [1], the extra time is compensated by the fact that the obtained DNN architecture is much simpler. This means that the optimized DNN architecture will be more efficient and faster to optimise/execute than the original DNN model. In the long run, this advantage will be cumulative and will be specially important given the NISQ nature of the current quantum machines, where the calibration data is continuously changing due to noise and errors. A comparison between the

Fig. 6. A zoom-in on a sample of P3 fitness value evolution

execution time of P3-DNN and SOTA-DNN will not be fair in this work considering that P3-DNN executes the DNN part on `python`, while P3 is executed in `C++` using a continuous communication between both parts.

6 Conclusion and Perspective

This work proposes an evolutionary deep neural network approach to solve the qubits' initialisation problem in IBM/NISQ/gate-based quantum machines. The proposal copes with the shortfalls of previous work, mainly on three aspects: (I) the correctness and completeness of the proposal, (II) a problem modelling that is correct and generalisable, and (III) diversity, usefulness and availability of the benchmarks. The experiments have been made using real calibration data of four IBM quantum machines, circuits for quantum optimisation and machine learning, and we compared our proposal with the state-of-the-art DNN model. The results showed that the proposed approach achieve better results using a simpler DNN model.

As a next step, it is planned to investigate the use of other linkage learning techniques such as LT-GOMEA, tackle the problem as a regression task, explore other ML techniques, include other quantum machines of different size, and build training datasets based on different metrics in addition to the circuits' depth.

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